

STABILITY OF METAL-CHELATE COMPOUNDS OF SOME VIOLURIC ACID DERIVATIVES

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Fe(II) forms deep blue complexes with violuric acid and its derivatives. A comparative study of the stabilities of the Fe(II) complexes with diphenylthiovioluric acid and the (*o*, *m* & *p*)-ditolylthiovioluric acids has been made by the spectrophotometric method. pK_a values of the three ligands have been determined by pH titrations against standard sodium hydroxide. It has been found that $\log K$ values of the chelates are related to pK_a values of the ligands. Introduction of the methyl group in the side benzene ring has been found to enhance the basic character of the ligands and also the stability of the metal chelates. The effect of the methyl group is most pronounced when it is situated in the *meta* position and is less when it is in the *para* position. Unexpectedly, the effect of methyl group has been found to be the least when it is present in the *ortho* position, and in this case steric factors seem to be involved.

Violuric acid derivatives have been found to form complexes with numerous metals by one of the authors (Singh, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 330; this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 57; 1960, 37, 569; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 245). The group $-\text{CO}-\text{C}(=\text{NOH})-$, contained in them, is analytically important since it confers upon the molecule the property of inner-complex salt formation. The chelates formed by ferrous iron with these reagents are deep blue in colour. The composition of the ferrous chelates corresponds to the formula FeX_2 , in which X represents a substituted violuric acid anion. In view of the formation of chelates by all these reagents with Fe(II), it has been considered worth while to determine the stability constants of these complexes for ascertaining how the substituents in the violuric acid molecule affect the stability of the chelates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diphenylthiovioluric acid and the three (*o*, *m*, and *p*)-ditolylthiovioluric acids were prepared by the methods described earlier (*loc. cit.*).

Determination of Stability Constants.—On account of the deep blue colour of the chelates formed by the reagents with ferrous iron, the spectrophotometric method was found to be convenient for determination of the stability constants. The use of this method requires a prior knowledge of the formula of the chelate under investigation. The formulas of the chelates studied were determined by analysis of the complexes thrown down as precipitates on the addition of the ammonium salt of the corresponding reagent to a saturated solution of a ferrous salt.

In the spectrophotometric method the optical density of the solution was used to determine the relative concentration of one of the components (usually the chelate) involved in the equilibrium. For the successful application of the method, only one substance should be coloured otherwise interference from other coloured substances must be avoided by applying a correction or by a close control of the wave length used. Further, Beer's law must hold for the coloured substance to be measured, which has been found to be the case for the systems investigated.

The stability constants of the ferrous chelates were determined by means of the following expression :

$$K = \frac{[\text{MKe}_2]}{[\text{M}] \times [\text{Ke}]^2}$$

Optical density measurements of the chelates were carried out in presence of a large excess of the corresponding reagent in each case so that the formation of the chelates could be considered to be complete. It is necessary therefore that the reagent in excess does not have even a weak

absorption at the wave length used. The coloured chelates were found to possess maximum absorption at $660 \text{ m}\mu$ at which wave length the reagents did not show any absorption. Measurements of optical densities were then made at such reagent concentrations that the formation of chelates was incomplete. The concentrations of the chelates were calculated directly from Beer's law. This gave the value of MK_e in the equation. Knowing the value of MK_e , the total quantity of Fe^{2+} present, and the total quantity of the chelating agent values of M and K_e could easily be determined; K was calculated in each case. The reagents being insoluble in water, optical density measurements were made in acetone-water mixtures. The proportion of acetone: water was maintained at 1 : 3 in all cases to facilitate comparison. The ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at a constant value by addition of potassium nitrate (0.2M) and as solutions of the reactants were very dilute, the activities of various constituents may be considered to remain unchanged and may be substituted by molar concentrations. To ensure the presence of iron completely in the ferrous state, a small quantity of hydroquinone was added before addition of the reagent. An excess of hydroquinone does not change the optical density of the system. The author had earlier found (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 335) that pH must be between 3.1 and 6.0 for maximum colour development. Consequently, pH of the solutions was maintained at 5.0 by using a buffer. Optical density measurements were made by using a spectrophotometer (Unicam, SP 600).

The following values of $\log_{10}K$ were calculated for the complexes of iron with different reagents :

Diphenylthioviolic acid	..	..	$\log_{10}K=5.20$
Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	..	..	$\log_{10}K=5.60$
Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	..	..	$\log_{10}K=5.80$
Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl	..	..	$\log_{10}K=6.08$

Each of the above values represents the mean of four values of $\log_{10}K$, determined from the results of measurement of optical densities of the solutions recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

$\text{KNO}_3=7 \text{ c.c.}$ Buffer=7 c.c. Total volume=28 c.c.

Diphenylthioviolic acid (0.05092 M) = $y \text{ c.c.}$
 $\text{Fe}^{2+}(0.000626M) = x \text{ c.c.}$

Di-*p*-tolylthioviolic acid (0.02098 M) = $y \text{ c.c.}$
 $\text{Fe}^{2+}(0.001224M) = x \text{ c.c.}$

Fe^{2+} soln.	Reagent.	O.D.	Fe^{2+} soln.	Reagent.	O.D.
6.8 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	0.022	2.0 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	0.590
2.0	5.0	0.220	6.5	0.5	0.130
6.8	0.2	0.020	2.0	5.0	0.585
2.0	5.0	0.200	6.5	0.5	0.129
6.8	0.2	0.021	2.0	5.0	0.580
2.0	5.0	0.210	6.5	0.5	0.128
6.8	0.2	0.020	2.0	5.0	0.590
2.0	5.0	0.210	6.5	0.5	0.131

TABLE II

KNO ₃ =7 c.c. Buffer=7 c.c. Total volume=28 c.c.			KNO ₃ =7 c.c. Buffer=7 c.c. Total volume=28 c.c.		
Di- <i>o</i> -tolylthioviolic acid (0.02252 M) = <i>y</i> c.c. Fe ²⁺ (0.001224 M) = <i>x</i> c.c.			Di- <i>m</i> -tolylthioviolic acid (0.021636 M) = <i>y</i> c.c. Fe ²⁺ (0.001224 M) = <i>x</i> c.c.		
Fe ²⁺ soln.	Reagent.	O.D.	Fe ²⁺ soln.	Reagent.	O.D.
2.0 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	0.540	2.0 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	0.633
6.5	0.5	0.070	6.5	0.5	0.231
2.0	5.0	0.550	2.0	5.0	0.625
6.5	0.5	0.072	6.5	0.5	0.227
2.0	5.0	0.545	2.0	5.0	0.630
6.5	0.5	0.071	6.5	0.5	0.230
2.0	5.0	0.540	2.0	5.0	0.640
6.5	0.5	0.070	6.5	0.5	0.235

The pK_a values of the four reagents were determined by pH titrations in 50 : 50 dioxan-water mixture with a view to studying the relationship between the pK_a values and $\log_{10}K$ values of the ferrous complexes. The following pK_a values were obtained.

Diphenylthioviolic acid	= 5.00
Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	= 5.35
Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	= 5.60
Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	= 5.90

DISCUSSION

The above pK_a values of the ligands are closely related to the $\log_{10}K$ values of the corresponding ferrous complexes; the order of pK_a values is the same as the order of stability constants of the corresponding ferrous complexes. There is a linear relationship between the two sets of values (Fig. 1).

The increase in the basic strength of the ligands and also the stability of the ferrous complexes due to introduction of the methyl group in the side benzene ring appear to be explainable on the basis of the electron-releasing property of the methyl group.

The order of the basic strength of the three ditolylthioviolic acids still remains to be explained. In this connection, it is interesting to note that Roberts (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 2181) found that the basic strength of substituted anilines was influenced to a greater extent when the substituent was present in the nearer *meta* position than in the more distant *para* position. Similar results were reported earlier by other workers (Kuhn and Zumstein, *Ber.*, 1926, **59**, 488; Pressman and Brown, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 540). It is therefore reasonable to suppose that the inductive effect of the methyl group would be experienced to a greater extent when the substituent is present in the *ortho* position, and would diminish when the methyl group is present in the *meta* position. The effect of the methyl group would

therefore be least when it is present in the *para* position on account of its greater distance from the reaction centre. In accordance with this view, di-*o*-tolylthiovioluric acid should be the strongest base and it should consequently furnish stablest complexes, while the basic strength of the *para* derivative should be the least.

The basic strength of di-*m*-tolylthiovioluric acid ($pK_a=5.9$) was found greater than that of the *para* compound ($pK_a=5.6$). This is according to expectations. But the basic strength of di-*o*-tolylthiovioluric acid and hence the stability of the corresponding complexes, which was expected to be greatest, was found to be the least ($pK_a=5.35$; $\log_{10}K=5.60$).

To explain the anomalous behaviour of di-*o*-tolylthiovioluric acid, the following resonating structures of the ferrous chelates are proposed.

In the above structures, due to the free rotation of the substituted benzene ring, the methyl group will not be able to pass the oxygen atom unless the chelate ring is distorted from its normal planar structure necessary for complete resonance. The distortion of the chelate ring would thus result in reducing the stabilising influence of resonance. This interpretation is supported by construction of molecular models. Alternatively, it is also likely that as a result of hyperconjugation, the C-atom of the methyl group attached to the benzene nucleus will become somewhat negative and one of its hydrogen atoms would then become positive due to no-bond resonance. The latter will then tend to form a hydrogen bond with the oxygen atom of the adjacent carbonyl group, reducing its co-ordinating capacity.